

FATIGUE LIFE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL POLYMER-MATRIX COMPOSITES CONSIDERING A WEIBULL PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION FOR THE BRITTLE FAILURE OF THE FIBERS

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SUMMARY: The difficulty in predicting lifetime for failure under oscillating loads is a major limitation in the application of many materials to structural components. This phenomenon, named fatigue, is an active field of research due to its engineering consequences in many different industrial fields. Polymer-matrix reinforced composite materials (PMC) are sensitive to fatigue. The classical approach for design against fatigue is based on phenomenological dependences of lifetime on amplitude and mean stress. These empiric models require extensive experimentation and, although they may be suitable for metals, they do not reproduce the characteristic behavior of composites. Indeed, the degradation of stiffness of PMC is not accounted for. An alternative approach to phenomenological models consists in considering the mechanisms that causes the damage in the composite. These models are referred to as mechanistic models and they aim to reproduce the evolution of mechanical properties as well as to extrapolate to different lamina orientations and ply design. The final purpose of this work is to develop a mechanistic model of fatigue damage of unidirectional composites based on the statistics of brittle fiber fragmentation. This model is based on previous works by other authors, which developed a theory of the fragmentation of a fiber embedded in a matrix based on the Weibull-Poisson probability distributions. This theory predicts the mean number of breaks that occur in a fiber under a static load. With the number of breaks and a shear-lag model assumption mechanical properties could be predicted like stiffness evolution. The mechanistic model proposed in this paper combines these theories with a crack growth law for glass fibers. The crack growth law is used to predict the evolution of the fiber strength probability distribution under an applied dynamical load. This new probability distribution is able to predict the mean number of breaks depending on load history. It also permits to predict the fatigue damage of a unidirectional composite in a global load sharing assumption

KEYWORDS: Fiber fragmentation, static fatigue, GFRP, crack growth.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymeric composites are widely used in structural applications because of their good specific stiffness,. These materials present an important anisotropy of their mechanical properties. Their damage mechanisms are completely different to the damage mechanisms that take place in metals. The damage is induced by fiber breaking, matrix cracking, debonding, delamination. There are also two classical approaches to study the damage: a mechanistic or a phenomenological approach. Phenomenological approaches require extensive experimentation and they do not reproduce the characteristic behavior of composites. An alternative to phenomenological models are the mechanistic models. These models consist in taking into account the mechanisms that causes the damage in the composite. In this paper a mechanistic damage model based on the fiber fragmentation leads to the stiffness loss simulation of a PMC under fatigue loads.

As it has been known for many years, brittle fibers such as glass or carbon, possess marked strength scatter due to the presence of surface flaws, introduced during manufacturing processes and handling.

When a load is applied to a composite, fiber fails stochastically at various flaws along them. The weaker fibers fail first whilst the stronger fibers will carry the applied load [1]. With increasing load, the fiber fractures into shorter and shorter fragments until the shear stress transfer, across the interface, is insufficient to cause further fracture of the fiber. At a fiber break, the axial load carried by the fiber is zero and it builds up, over a certain distance, to a plateau or far field value which is approximately $E_f \epsilon$, (where E_f is the fiber's Young Modulus and ϵ is the composite strain). This stress redistribution involves a reduction of the apparent stiffness of the composite.

Fiber breaks occur when the applied load is higher than the fiber strength. In the case of glass-fibre reinforced polymers, GFRP, fiber strength is also dependent on time due to the static fatigue of glass. In this paper the phenomena of static fatigue is also introduced in the formulation of the damage model. This allows to predict the evolution of composite properties in function of time.

FIBER STRENGTH

The glass fiber strength calculated from the inter-atomic bonds is very high; however the real or nominal strength of the major glass objects is much lower. This difference is due to two factors: the existence of micro-defects on the glass surface and the growth of these defects with time, if the glass is stressed in presence of humidity (static fatigue).

The treatment of the glass fracture should be based on the knowledge of the size and distribution of surface flaws and the dynamics of crack (or flaw) growth (influence of the humidity, stress and temperature in the flaw rate growth). A review of glass fracture [2] describes these aspects.

1. Static strength

First, the fracture of glass object, without considering the influence of the static fatigue, is taken up. Glass fracture is produced when the stress intensity factor K_I , exceeds the mode I glass fracture toughness, K_{IC} :

$$K_I > K_{IC} \quad \text{Eqn.1}$$

The stress intensity factor K_I is determined from the applied stress, σ , the crack length, a , and a geometric factor, Y :

$$K_I = \sigma \cdot Y \cdot \sqrt{a} \quad \text{Eqn.2}$$

The fracture strength is obtained when K_I reaches K_{IC} , taking the highest flaw of the material, a_{max} :

$$\sigma^u = \frac{K_{IC}}{Y \cdot \sqrt{a_{max}}} \quad \text{Eqn.3}$$

In other words, the strength depends on the highest flaw present on the surface, and intrinsic factors of the material.

The flaws (or micro-flaws), presents on the surface of a glass object, show high size variability. This variability can be modeled with a statistic distribution, so the strength of a glass object exhibits a high scatter. The Weibull distribution [3] is widely used for the description of the glass strength variability [4]. Using this distribution, the fracture probability of a fiber of length L , subjected to a certain stress, σ , is modeled with a cumulative Weibull distribution:

$$P(\sigma, L) = 1 - e^{-\frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^p} \quad \text{Eqn.4}$$

where L_0 is a length scale factor, σ_0 is a strain scale factor and ρ is the Weibull coefficient. Higher ρ coefficients decrease the variability on the fracture strength values. Conversely, with the same applied strain, longer fibers have a higher fracture probability.

2. Static fatigue

Glass strength degradation in presence of humidity has been explained by different ways, but the nature of this corrosion reaction [2] under stresses (or strains) has not been clarified yet. It is often assumed that it is caused by the rupture of the Si-O connection in presence of humidity:

The key for the life prediction of a glass fiber is to know the crack growth rate as a function of the more relevant parameters (humidity, temperature and stress). Several rate growth laws exist, but the most widely used is a potential law:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = A \left(\frac{K_I}{K_{Ic}} \right)^n \quad \text{Eqn.5}$$

where A and n are empirical parameters. In this expression the growth rate dependency with the applied stress and the crack size is implicit, through the stress intensity factor (K_I). The dependency on the temperature is introduced in the parameter A .

Substituting the equation 2 into equation 5, and integrating along the time, the flaw size as a function of time is obtained:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = A \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma(t) \cdot Y \cdot \sqrt{a(t)}}{K_{Ic}} \right)^n \quad \text{Eqn. 6}$$

$$a(t)^{1-n/2} = a_0^{1-n/2} + \left(1 - \frac{n}{2}\right) \cdot A \cdot \left(\frac{Y}{K_{Ic}}\right)^n \cdot \int_t \sigma(\tau)^n \cdot d\tau \quad \text{Eqn.7}$$

Equation 7 gives the flaw size at time t , of an initial flaw of size a_0 , under a applied stress field, $\sigma(t)$. An initial flaw of size a_0 , has associated a ultimate strength, $\sigma^u(0)$. The relation is obtained from equation 3:

$$a_0 = \left(\frac{K_{Ic}}{Y \cdot \sigma^u(0)} \right)^2 \quad \text{Eqn.8}$$

In the same way, at a time t , the new crack size, $a(t)$, has associated a ultimate strength, $\sigma^u(t)$. Substituting these values in equation 7, a relation between the ultimate strength at time t and the initial ultimate strength is computed using the following equation,

$$\left(\sigma^u(t)\right)^{n-2} = B \cdot \int_t \sigma(\tau)^n \cdot d\tau + \left(\sigma^u(0)\right)^{n-2} \quad \text{Eqn.9}$$

where B is the material constant (under isothermal conditions) given by equation 10.

$$B = \left(1 - \frac{n}{2}\right) \cdot A \cdot \left(\frac{Y}{K_{Ic}}\right)^2 \quad \text{Eqn.10}$$

Equation 9 gives the degradation of the ultimate strength due to static fatigue, when a glass fiber is stressed by a stress history, $\sigma(t)$. When a composite is stressed during time, some fiber flaws growth until fracture. A fiber breaks if its ultimate strength at time t , $\sigma^u(t)$, is smaller than the applied stress, $\sigma(t)$, i.e., $\sigma^u(t) \leq \sigma(t)$. It is useful to predict the probability of a fiber break, due to static fatigue, from the initial Weibull distribution. A fiber will break after the stress history given by $\sigma(t)$ if its initial strength, $\sigma^u(0)$, is smaller than a certain value, σ^* which could be computed arranging terms equation 9,

$$\sigma^* = \left((\sigma(t))^{n-2} - B \cdot \int_t \sigma(\tau)^n \cdot d\tau \right)^{\frac{1}{n-2}} \quad \text{Eqn.11}$$

a. *Static fatigue under a constant load*

The equation 9 permits the calculation of the strength of a single fiber after a stress history of duration t . From this result, it is possible to establish the statistical strength distribution of a multiplicity of fibers at instant t . At that moment, some of the fibers would have broken due to applied load history. The Weibull distribution of eq. 4 represents the variability of the flaw sizes on the fiber surface. Therefore, to determine the strength distribution the following approach has been followed. First, the flaw length associated to any strength in the distribution has been calculated. Then, it is assumed that each flaw grows according to the equation 7. Finally, the strength associated to each flaw at instant t is recalculated. The new statistical distribution of the strength probability will be as shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Ultimate strength probability evolution. —■— Initial strength probability, —◆— strength probability at time t_1 , —▲— predicted value with the initial strength probability. A constant load of $\sigma=1500\text{MPa}$ is applied until time $t_1=2 \cdot 10^4\text{s}$ to fibers with Weibull parameters: $\sigma_0=5000\text{MPa}$ and $\rho=8$. Strength and crack growth parameters: $A=0.022$, $n=25$, $K_{ic}=0.75 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5}$, $Y=\pi$.

Figure 1 shows the strength distribution at $t=0$ and after a constant applied stress applied during t_1 . At t_1 , approximately 32% of the fibers would have broken. This new strength probability could be predicted from equation 11. If a static load is assumed, i.e. $\sigma(t) = \sigma$, equation 11 takes the form:

$$\sigma^* = \left(\sigma^{n-2} - B \cdot \sigma^n \cdot t \right)^{\frac{1}{n-2}} \quad \text{Eqn.12}$$

Taking the example of figure 1, the initial ultimate strength prediction equivalent to the effect of crack growth (given with equation 12) gives a crack probability of 31.3%, instead of a probability of 32%, as given by the recalculated strength distribution.

b. *Static fatigue under a sinusoidal load*

Consider now the case that the load is sinusoidal, i.e.,

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_a + \sigma_b \sin(t) \quad \text{Eqn.13}$$

If it is introduced in equation 11, the equation can be rewritten as:

$$\sigma^* = \left(\sigma(t)^{n-2} - B \cdot \sigma_a^n \cdot g(n, \zeta) \cdot t \right)^{\frac{1}{n-2}} \quad \text{Eqn.14}$$

where $g(n, \zeta)$ is given by the next equation and ζ is the relative amplitude, i.e, $\zeta = \frac{\sigma_b}{\sigma_a}$ [5] .

$$g(n, \zeta) = \sum_{l=0}^{n/2} \left[\frac{n! \cdot \left(\frac{\zeta}{2} \right)^{2l}}{(n-2l)! \cdot (l!)^2} \right] \quad \text{Eqn.15}$$

DEGRADATION MODEL

A degradation model for predicting the stiffness evolution due to the fiber breakage is needed.

1. *Fiber fragmentation*

When a fiber breaks, the axial stress carried by the fiber is zero, and the load is transferred by the shear stress that appears at the interface between the fiber and the matrix, as shown in figure 3. The axial load carried by the fiber increases from zero, at a fiber break, until a constant stress (called far-field stress) at a certain distance from the fiber break. The length of this zone, where the stress is smaller than the far-field value, is called *load recovery region*. This stress redistribution due to the fiber breaks cause a lose of the apparent stiffness of the composite, so it is very important to know the number of breaks occurred at a certain stress, which will be used for predicting the stiffness degradation.

From equation 4 it could be shown that the number of breaks in the fiber follows a Poisson law [6]. With this assumption, the mean number of breaks in a fiber of length L under load σ is:

$$\langle N \rangle = \frac{L}{L_0} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\rho \quad \text{Eqn.16}$$

This result is widely used in the literature to compute the Weibull parameters (σ_0, ρ) from the experimental results. Anyway, this result is only valid at initial fragmentation stages, because as the number of breaks increases, some flaws will be obscured in the *load recovery region* (the stresses in this zone are smaller than the *far-field* stress and no more breaks could appear in this zone).

Once the mean number of breaks is known, the distance between the breaks, i.e, the length of the different fragments in which the fiber has split, has to be computed. From the statistic laws it can be shown that if the number of breaks follows a Poisson law, then the distance between two consecutive breaks follows an exponential law [7], then:

$$f(x) = \Lambda \cdot e^{-\Lambda \cdot x} \quad \text{Eqn.17}$$

where Λ is the number of breaks per unit length, and it is computed from equation 16:

$$\Lambda = \frac{\langle N \rangle}{L} = \frac{1}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\rho \quad \text{Eqn.18}$$

This assumption is valid for an infinitely long fiber and at the initial fragmentation stages. Many authors [8-9] compute other distribution functions to take into account higher break densities. However, they do not take into account the effect of the finite length of the fiber (or size effect). Andersons and co-workers [10] dealt with this problem and propose a distribution function that takes into account the size effect, but only at the initial fragmentation stages. In this work the effect of the finite fiber length is taken into account in the formulation of the apparent mean fiber stress.

2. Fiber fragmentation due to static fatigue

Due to the static fatigue, it has been shown that the fracture probability of a fiber increases with time, because of the crack growth of inherent flaws in the surface of the fiber. Due to this effect, the number of breaks will increase with time. To consider this effect equation 18 should be modified taking the value σ^* from equation 11 instead of the applied stress σ . The new break density is:

$$\Lambda = \frac{1}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma_0} \right)^\rho \quad \text{Eqn. 19}$$

Next plot shows the evolution of the break density due to static fatigue. The glass fiber parameters are those considered in figure 1.

Fig. 2. Break density due to static fatigue. A constant load of $\sigma=1500\text{MPa}$ is applied to fibers with Weibull parameters: $\sigma_0=5000\text{MPa}$ and $\rho=8$. Strength and crack growth parameters considered are $\Lambda=0.022$, $n=25$, $K_{ic}=0.75 \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, $Y=\pi$.

3. Average fiber stress

As it has been shown in previous subsections, some flaws of a fiber will grow and crack under the applied load. These cracks or fiber breaks cause a new stress re-distribution along the fiber. Near a fiber break the load is carried by the shear stress between fiber and matrix (see figure 3).

Fig. 3. At a fiber break the axial load carried by the fiber is zero. The load is carried by the shear stress that appears at the interface between the fiber and the matrix.

This new stress re-distribution near fiber breaks has been widely studied. There are many different models, named *shear-lag models*. Cox and co-workers [11] formulated first a shear-lag model, which predicts the real stress near the breaks. But the formulation of the Cox's model is quite complex (with hyperbolic functions), so in this paper a simplified linear shear-lag model is used. This model, which was first introduced by Kelly-Tyson [12], assumes a linear increase of the axial stress from a fiber break, until a certain distance from it. At this distance, called load recovery region, the stress reaches the *far-field stress*, see figure 4. According to the Kelly-Tyson shear-lag model, the length of this load recovery region, l_{ex} , is obtained from the far-field stress, $E_f \epsilon$, the radius of the fiber, r , and the maximum shear stress, τ , between the fiber and the matrix before fiber debonding or matrix yielding.

$$l_{ex} = \frac{r E_f \cdot \epsilon}{\tau} \quad \text{Eqn.20}$$

From this stress redistribution, the average fiber stress, σ_m , along the fiber can be computed. The average stress in the fiber is obtained by the quotient between the integrated axial stress along all fiber fragments and the fiber length:

$$\sigma_m = \langle \Sigma(L) \rangle = \int \Sigma(x) \cdot f(x) \cdot dx \quad \text{Eqn.21}$$

where $f(x)$ is the fragment length distribution given with equation 17, and $\Sigma(x)$ the average stress in a fiber of length x . This integral is done in two parts. First, the average stress corresponding to the axial stress profile along a fiber fragment of length x is computed. Then, this average axial strength is integrated over all fiber fragments. For computing the average axial stresses for a fiber fragment of length x , is necessary to distinguish whether the fiber fragment is greater to two times the length of the load recovery region ($2 \cdot l_{ex}$), or not.

Fig. 4. Kelly-Tyson's shear lag model. Stress profile at a fragment of broken fiber. At a break the axial stress is zero and it increases until it reaches the far-field stress ($E_f \epsilon$). This region is called load recovery region, and has a length of l_{ex} .

a. Average stress in a fiber of length: $2 \cdot l_{ex} \leq x$

In a fiber of length x bigger than two times the stress recovery region, the stress profile assuming a linear shear-lag model, is shown in figure 4. The average stress is given by the following equation:

$$\sigma_m = E_f \cdot \epsilon \cdot \left(1 - \frac{l_{ex}}{x} \right) \quad \text{Eqn.22}$$

b. Average stress in a fiber of length $x < 2 \cdot l_{ex}$

In a fiber shorter than two times the stress recovery region the far-field stress could not be reached. Then,

$$\sigma_m = E_f \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \frac{x}{4 \cdot l_{ex}} \quad \text{Eqn.23}$$

c. Average fiber stress along the whole fragmented fiber with initial length L

It is necessary to define the $\Sigma(x)$, for computing the average fiber stress along the whole fragmented fiber.

- If the distance between breaks is shorter than two times the stress recovery region, then $\Sigma(x)$ is given by equation 22.
- If the distance between breaks is greater than two times the stress recovery region but shorter than the initial fiber length L , then $\Sigma(x)$ is given by equation 23.
- If the distance between breaks is greater than the initial fiber length, L , then $\Sigma(x)$ is equal to the far-field stress.

With these assumptions, the piecewise function $\Sigma(x)$ is formulated as follows

$$\Sigma(x) = \begin{cases} E_f \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \frac{x}{4 \cdot l_{ex}} & x \leq 2 \cdot l_{ex} \\ E_f \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \left(1 - \frac{l_{ex}}{x}\right) & 2 \cdot l_{ex} \leq x \leq L \\ E_f \cdot \varepsilon & x \geq L \end{cases} \quad \text{Eqn.24}$$

Then equation 21 leads to:

$$\sigma_m = E_f \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \left(\int_0^{2 \cdot l_{ex}} \frac{x}{4 \cdot l_{ex}} \cdot f(x) dx + \int_{2 \cdot l_{ex}}^L \left(1 - \frac{l_{ex}}{x}\right) \cdot f(x) dx + \int_L^{\infty} f(x) dx \right) \quad \text{Eqn.25}$$

where $f(x)$ is given by equation 17. The analytic solution of previous equation is given by:

$$\sigma_m = E_f \cdot \varepsilon \cdot \left(\frac{1 - e^{-2l_{ex}\Lambda}}{4l_{ex}\Lambda} + \frac{e^{-2l_{ex}\Lambda}}{2} + \Lambda l_{ex} [\Gamma(0, \Lambda L) - \Gamma(0, 2l_{ex}\Lambda)] \right) \quad \text{Eqn.26}$$

where $\Gamma(0, x)$ is the *Gamma* function as follows:

$$\Gamma(0, x) = \int_x^{\infty} \frac{e^{-t}}{t} dt \quad \text{Eqn.27}$$

DAMAGE MODEL

In order to develop a damage model, from equation 26 a damage variable can be defined. In other words, if the stress-strain relation at the fiber is formulated in terms of a damage variable, d , by comparing equations 28 and 26, d is:

$$\sigma_m = (1 - d) E_f \cdot \varepsilon \quad \text{Eqn.28}$$

$$d = 1 - \left(\frac{1 - e^{-2l_{ex}\Lambda}}{4l_{ex}\Lambda} + \frac{e^{-2l_{ex}\Lambda}}{2} + \Lambda l_{ex} [\Gamma(0, \Lambda L) - \Gamma(0, 2l_{ex}\Lambda)] \right) \quad \text{Eqn.1}$$

For proofing the thermodynamically consistence of this damage model, a more rigorous formulation must be done, establishing the free energy of the problem, the damage criteria, internal variables evolution, tangent constitutive law. This procedure would overcome the extension of this paper. However, the thermodynamically consistence is explained here in an ‘intuitive’ way: The internal variable of the damage model is the break density, Λ . From the Clausius-Plank inequality, and using the Coleman theorem [15], it can be shown that for proving the thermodynamically consistence of the damage model the derivate of the damage variable must be positive, i.e., $\dot{d} \geq 0$. This inequality will be satisfied whenever the derivation of the break density is bigger or equal than zero, i.e., $\dot{\Lambda} \geq 0$. This means that the number of breaks can not decrease, which it is always accomplished, because if the number of breaks decrease, this would means that two fragments has been joined, so the thermodynamically consistence is proven.

The next step is to show how this fiber damage is introduced in the formulation of the composite constitutive laws. The following hypothesis or simplifications of the model must be done. In a composite, when a fiber breaks, the load is transferred, to the others fibers of the section. Two models can be used. The first one is to consider that the load is transferred homogeneously to the others fibers of the section. This assumption is called *global load sharing* (GLS) and it is useful at the first fragmentation stages, when the formation and growth of clusters is not important. Another approach is to consider the stress concentrations at the fibers near the broken one. This is called *local load sharing* (LLS). Since the formulation of the damage model for the fiber has been done for initial fragmentation stages, a GLS situation is considered for the formulation of the composite damage model. This involves a series of limitations to the model, because a GLS assumption cannot predict the formation of clusters and their growth, which will cause the failure of the composite. However it could be used for the prediction of the stiffness reduction of the composite, for example.

The constitutive relation for the composite is done using the mixity law. Then the stress-strain relation comes from equation 30, where d_f is the damage occurred in the fiber, given by equation 29. d_m is the matrix damage, E_m and E_f the matrix and fiber Young modulus, and σ and ϵ the stress and strain of the composite. In this paper, the matrix damage is neglected.

$$\sigma = [(1-d_f)E_f + (1-d_m)E_m] \epsilon \quad \text{Eqn.2}$$

RESULTS AND SIMULATION

a. Comparison of static and cyclic behavior

The stiffness reduction will be different if the applied load is constant or if it is changing during time. If the applied load is constant the break density is obtained from equation 18, instead of the equation 19, which is used for a sinusoidal load. The differences are shown in figure 5. The stiffness reduction of a fiber with a constant load applied, σ , is compared with two sinusoidal loads: one with maximum amplitude equal to σ , and the other with a mean value equal to σ . The stiffness reduction is bigger in the third case.

Fig. 1. Stiffness reduction in a glass fiber. The glass fiber considered is the same as in figure 1.

b. Comparison with experimental values

The model is compared with experimental results obtained from [13]. Some fatigue tests are done with composites with different fiber orientation and the stiffness reduction is measured. Figure 6 show the experimental values obtained with a composite with the 98% the fibers parallels to the load, and the matrix's Young modulus is smaller than the fiber modulus. Then the major influence in stiffness reduction is given from the damage induced in the fibers. A good agreement between the experimental results and the predicted ones is observed.

Fig. 6. Comparison between predicted stiffness reduction and experimental values given in [13].

CONCLUSIONS

A mechanistic damage model, which takes into account static fatigue for GFRP, is formulated. This model is useful for the prediction of stiffness reduction in a GFRP composite, but it is not able to predict fracture. This model is useful for describing the frequency dependence detected in classical fatigue test [14].

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